

**University of
Zurich** ^{UZH}

Performance study of the IDEA Vertex Detector for FCC-ee

Author:

Kimia Mirbaghestan

Supervisor:

Dr. Armin Ilg

Physics Institute, University of Zurich

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Abstract

With the discovery of the Higgs boson in 2012, the Standard Model of Particle Physics (SM) is complete. However, many experimental observations still remain unexplained by the SM, indicating that it is not the ultimate theory of nature. Despite this, the SM predictions agree well with experimental results, suggesting that the energy scale of New Physics (NP) could be either beyond the TeV scale or below it but with weak coupling. Therefore, to discover NP, advanced collider experiments that can reach centre-of-mass energy at the TeV scale and have a large integrated luminosity are needed. The Future Circular Collider (FCC) is a proposed state-of-the-art facility to tackle these challenges. The first phase, FCC-ee, a high-luminosity electron-positron collider, aims to serve as a Higgs, electroweak, flavour, and top-quark factory, with the first collisions expected around 2045. The second phase, FCC-hh, will feature proton-proton collisions at a center-of-mass energy of around 100 TeV.

In this work, the performance of the IDEA vertex detector for FCC-ee was studied using the detailed full simulation detector model. The focus was on the resolution of impact parameters, which is critical for precise vertexing. The simulation results indicate that the dependence of the resolution on the azimuthal angle is of the order 22 % for momentum equal to 1 GeV (14 % for momentum = 100 GeV), which reveals that the impact of uneven material distribution in the detailed vertex detector is not drastic. Gaps in detector coverage were identified at certain angles, leading to anomalies in track reconstruction, which highlight areas for design improvements in future studies of the detector.

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Introduction

The Standard Model (SM) of particle physics [1–4] is the currently accepted theory that describes the known fundamental constituents of matter and their interactions except gravity. Its last missing piece, the Higgs boson, was discovered in 2012 at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) [5, 6]. The SM classifies the fundamental particles into two broad categories: fermions and bosons. Fermions, which follow Fermi-Dirac statistics, are the matter particles and include quarks and leptons. The quarks come in three families, with two quarks in each family. The bound states of quarks form protons, neutrons, and other hadrons. Leptons include the electron, muon, tau, and their corresponding neutrinos. Bosons, which follow Bose-Einstein statistics, are mostly force-carrying particles that mediate the fundamental interactions. These include the photon (electromagnetic force), W and Z bosons (weak force), and gluons (strong force). The only spin-0 boson, the Higgs boson, is responsible for giving mass to quarks, leptons and weak interaction bosons via electroweak symmetry breaking [7–10].

The SM, however, can neither account for the nonvanishing neutrino masses observed via neutrino oscillations nor for the astrophysical evidence for Dark Matter, the accelerated expansion of the universe (Dark Energy) or the indications for an inflationary era. Furthermore, the Sakharov conditions [11] for generating a matter-anti-matter asymmetry are not fulfilled in the SM, since there is no strong first-order electroweak phase transition and the amount of charge-parity (CP) violation in the SM (originating from the CKM and PMNS matrix) is insufficient. This means that the SM cannot explain 95 % of the energy content of the universe (Dark Matter and Dark Energy) and for the excess of matter over anti-matter, etc. Therefore, it is certain from these observations that the SM cannot be a complete theory that describes nature.

Despite this, the SM predictions so far agree well with collider experiments, which suggests that the New Physics (NP) scale could be either beyond the TeV scale or below it but with a small production cross-section. Therefore, one of the ways to discover NP is to develop advanced high-energy particle colliders, which can reach either a center-of-mass energy at the TeV scale or make very precise measurements at the GeV scale. This is because precision measurements can reveal quantum corrections from heavy TeV scale NP particles appearing as loops in higher-order Feynman diagrams. For both types of colliders, large integrated luminosity is needed to produce rare events with a small production cross-section. This is because the number of events (N) for a given process

$$N = \sigma L \quad \text{where, } L = \int \mathcal{L} dt \quad (0.0.1)$$

is equal to the product of the cross section (σ) and the integrated luminosity (L).

Figure 1: Dominant Feynman diagrams for the Higgs, top, electroweak, and Z factories, respectively.

In this report, we will precisely study one such proposed collider, the Future Circular Collider (FCC), which is proposed to succeed the Large Electron Positron Collider (LEP) and Large Hadron Collider (LHC) projects. The first stage of FCC is a high luminosity and high energy e^+e^- collider [12, 13], named FCC-ee, whose goal is to produce an enormous number of events containing Higgs bosons, W and Z bosons, and different flavour quarks. Some of the leading order Feynman diagrams are shown in Fig. 1. There are many other proposed e^+e^- colliders, such as the ILC, CLIC, CEPC, and FCC-ee [13]. In this report, FCC-ee is discussed. The advantage of this collider is that it has four interaction points (IP) compared to other proposed colliders. FCC-ee has high luminosity, and, therefore, high number of collision events. It operates at the center-of-mass energy around the Z pole ($m_z = 91.2$ GeV), around the WW threshold (161 GeV), as a Higgs factory (240 GeV), and around the $t\bar{t}$ threshold (340-350 and 365 GeV). A proposed timeline of the different runs is shown in Fig. 2b, and the cross-section of different SM processes at an e^+e^- collider is shown in Fig. 2a.

Therefore, FCC-ee is one of the most advanced proposed e^+e^- colliders and has good potential to unveil NP and guide particle physics towards the correct extension of the SM. Hence, in this report, we are particularly interested in developing detectors for FCC-ee. After the potential approval of FCC-ee, the first collision of FCC-ee is scheduled to be around 2045. The second stage of FCC is FCC-hh, which would have a centre-of-mass energy of 100 TeV and will start in 2070. This is, however, beyond the scope of this report.

At FCC-ee, as already mentioned, four IPs exist, where experiments will measure the collision products. Each experiment might have a dedicated vertex detector, which is closest to the IP in the detector and is used along with a tracker to determine the location of the primary, secondary and tertiary interaction vertices. Precise determination of the location of these vertices is crucial for efficient flavour tagging of jets, precise flight distance measurements and reconstruction of complex decay chains involving heavy jets as well as tau leptons. In this report, we examine the performance of the Innovative Detector for Electron-positron Accelerator (IDEA) [15] vertex detector with full simulation.

The report is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly discusses the basic techniques for tracking and vertex detection at the FCC-ee. In Section 3, the experimental setup is discussed along with a brief overview of the IDEA and CLIC-Like Detector (CLD) detectors [16, 17]. In Section 4, the main results of this work are presented along with a brief qualitative discussion. Finally, in Section 5, we give our conclusion and future work.

Figure 2: (a) Production cross-section of different SM processes as a function of the center of mass energy of an e^+e^- collider [14]. (b) Proposed run plan showing the evolution of the integrated luminosity for the four phases of operation of FCC-ee over time [13].

1 Tracking and Vertexing at FCC-ee

The main purpose of particle detectors is to accurately reconstruct particle collisions after hard scattering. This involves measuring the properties of the particles created during the collision and correctly identifying them by analyzing how the particles interact with the different parts of the detector.

The coordinate system of the FCC-ee detectors is shown in Fig. 1.1. In this plot, the z -axis is the direction of the motion of the beam of colliding particles, and ϕ and θ are the azimuthal and zenith angles.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the different angles in the coordinate system in the FCC detector.¹

The key components of a typical particle detector include the vertex detector, which identifies where vertices are produced; the tracker, which measures the paths of the charged particles; a magnet that bends their trajectories to determine the particle momenta; calorimeters that measure the energy of the particles; and muon detectors that specifically detect and locate muons. Each of these components plays a crucial role in identifying particles and understanding the collision event with the highest possible efficiency and accuracy. Fig. 1.2 shows the detector components and how different particles interact with them. Charged particles are deflected by the magnetic field, allowing the tracker to measure their curvature and, thus, their momentum. Neutral particles, such as Neutrons, do not interact with the tracker but deposit their energy in the calorimeters, providing information about their energy and direction.

The tracking system is the innermost layer of the detector and has two distinct components: vertex detectors and trackers. Since in this report, we study the performance of the tracking system only, we briefly discuss below the working principles of the tracking and vertex detectors.

¹Source: [CMS coordinate system example](#)

Figure 1.2: Schematic drawing of a particle detector, in which different types of particles leave different traces [18].

1.1 Particle matter Ionization

As a charged particle passes through the different layers of the detector, it interacts with the detector material and ionizes it. This process is critical for particle detectors as this ionization generates some signals and will be used to reconstruct the tracks of the particles and measure their properties.

Traversing particles lose energy as they pass through matter due to ionization and excitation of atoms in the material. The energy loss per unit path length $\frac{dE}{dx}$ for a particle of charge z and velocity v in a material is described by the Bethe–Bloch formula, which is approximately given by:

$$\frac{dE}{dx} = \frac{4\pi e^4 z^2}{m_e c^2 \beta^2} \cdot \frac{Z}{A} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{2m_e c^2 \beta^2 \gamma^2 T_{\max}}{I^2} \right) - \beta^2 \quad (1.1.1)$$

In this equation, e is the electron charge, m_e is the electron mass, c is the speed of light, γ is the Lorentz factor, Z is the atomic number of the material, A is the atomic mass of the material, T_{\max} is the maximum kinetic energy that can be transferred to a single electron in a collision, I is the mean excitation energy of the material [19].

This particle requires to have minimal energy to ionize the detector material (minimal ionising particle, MIP). It is especially important because it helps predict how far particles can travel in a medium before losing all their energy.

1.2 Track and vertex reconstruction

Reconstruction of the trajectory of the charged particles is crucial, as it then allows us to identify different particles and measure their momentum.

In the next step, the tracks are used to reconstruct the different vertices of the event. According to Fig. 1.4, from the reconstructed tracks, the vertices of the decaying particles can be found. In general, there can be more than one vertex (Fig. 1.4 shows the primary, secondary, and tertiary vertices); in particular, heavy particles such as τ and B -hadron can fly a short distance before decaying since they have a longer lifetime compared to other heavy particles. Lifetime of these two particles are $3 \times 10^{-13}s$ and $1.5 \times 10^{-12}s$ [20], respectively. Therefore, in order to identify them, it is also important to reconstruct the position of the secondary vertices.

Figure 1.4: The illustration of the primary, secondary, and tertiary vertices. [SLD collab].

An important metric to gauge how well a detector is able to reconstruct vertices is the resolution of the impact parameters, which can be calculated through:

$$\sigma(d_0) = a \oplus \frac{b}{p \sin^{3/2} \theta} = \sqrt{a^2 + \left(\frac{b}{p \sin^{3/2} \theta} \right)^2} \quad (1.2.4)$$

where a and b are asymptotic resolutions and the uncertainty from multiple scattering, respectively. In the reference [12], a and b are equal to constant $4 \mu m$ and $15 \mu m$, respectively. In this equation, b is the dependence of the material budget on the resolution.

1.3 Material budget and multiple scattering

Material budget is an important detector property for tracking and vertexing. When a charged particle passes through the material, it gets scattered multiple times by the nuclei of the materials used in the tracking system. Therefore, the trajectory of the particle changes and the final position is relocated from the actual location by angular deviation of θ_0 , which can be calculated:

$$\theta_0 = \frac{13.6 \text{ MeV}}{\beta pc} z \sqrt{\frac{x}{X_0}} \left(1 + 0.038 \ln \left(\frac{x}{X_0} \right) \right). \quad (1.3.1)$$

where x , X_0 , p , βc , and z are the thickness of the material, the radiation length, momentum, and charge of the particle, respectively [19].

The effect of the material budget on the resolution of the impact parameter is depicted in Fig. 1.5. The dotted lines indicate the fits with the approximation introduced in Eq. 1.2.4 [21]. According to the plot, the reduction of the material budget improves the resolution of the impact parameter.

Figure 1.5: The effect of the material budget on the d_0 impact parameter resolution in the FCC-ee in the fast simulation.

1.4 FCC-ee detector concept

A variety of detectors have been proposed for the FCC-ee collider, including the CLD and IDEA detectors. The concepts behind these detector designs are explained in the following sections.

1.4.1 CLD detector concept

The CLD detector is modeled after a design from the CLIC detector [17]. It includes a silicon pixel vertex detector and a silicon-based tracker. These are followed by highly granular calorimeters: a silicon-tungsten electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) and a scintillator-steel hadronic calorimeter (HCAL). A 2T magnetic field is generated by a superconducting solenoid, and a steel yoke with embedded resistive plate chambers (RPCs) for muon detection is used to contain the magnetic field. The layout of the CLD system is illustrated in Fig. 1.6.

1.4.2 IDEA detector concept

The IDEA detector design [22], shown in Fig. 1.7, features a vertex detector placed at the centre, just outside the beam pipe. Surrounding this is a lightweight drift chamber, followed by an outer silicon

Figure 1.6: The schematic of the CLD detector.

wrapper used for tracking. Beyond the tracking system, there is a dual-readout calorimeter with a pre-shower system, and the muon detection system is located in the return yoke at the outermost region of the detector.

Figure 1.7: The schematic of the IDEA detector.

1.4.3 Difference between CLD and IDEA vertex detectors

The proposed vertex detectors for FCC-ee are light vertex detectors based on DMAPS technology and have a small material budget. In order to test the performance of the vertex detector concepts, *full simulation* is used to simulate the interaction of particles with the detector using Geant4. The CLD vertex detector model was implemented in full simulation using DD4hep, which is shown in Fig. 1.8. This model is less detailed compared to the newly developed vertex detector of the IDEA detector concept shown in Fig. 1.9a [22].

In the CLD vertex detector, $r_{min} = 13mm$, and in the IDEA vertex detector, it is $13.7mm$. This means that in the CLD vertex detector, the vertex detector is closer to the IP, and it is easier for particles to be detected. This is one advantage of CLD over the IDEA vertex detector.

Figure 1.8: The schematic of the CLD vertex detector in DD4hep.

In the CLD vertex detector, there are three double-layer barrel layers and disks, while in IDEA, there are three single-layer inner barrel layers and three single-hit disks and two single-hit outer barrel layers. This means the CLD vertex detector can register up to six hits, whereas the IDEA detector can register up to five hits. For the CLD, $0.6\text{--}0.7\% \frac{X}{X_0}$ per double layer and for the IDEA $0.25\% \frac{X}{X_0}$ per single layer, which means CLD has more material budget. Although having more hits makes detection easier, the primary focus of the IDEA design is to minimize the material budget.

Additionally, the IDEA detector benefits from fully engineered designs, whereas the CLD detector lacks such detailed engineering. In IDEA, every component, from the barrel to the disks, has been carefully and precisely designed. In contrast, the CLD detector follows a more simplified conceptual design, focusing primarily on basic functionality rather than detailed engineering optimization.

In the CLD vertex detector, the endcap and barrel have a simple structure. The IDEA vertex detector, however, modified the CLD vertex constructor code to enable the implementation of a more detailed vertex detector for IDEA. In Fig. 1.9b, the inner barrel part of the vertex detector and the individual sensors are implemented along the stave. In this Figure, the yellow parts are the sensitive parts of the sensors, and the green parts are insensitive. This means that there are some areas per stave in the $(r - \phi)$ plane, which is insensitive. These gaps in coverage are covered by an overlap with the next stave. For the vertex disk, the staves are placed in the $x - y$ plane to build a petal covering 1/8th of the disk. This repeated for all disks to form the endcaps on the two sides of the barrel.

Another important difference between the CLD and IDEA vertex detectors is their material budget's dependence on the azimuthal angle ϕ . In the CLD vertex detector, the material budget remains uniform, showing no significant variation as ϕ changes [17]. This uniformity is beneficial for consistent tracking performance across all directions. In contrast, the IDEA vertex detector exhibits fluctuations in the material budget depending on ϕ , as shown in Fig. 1.10. These variations arise from the specific arrangement of the detector components in the stave and the overlap of the staves. As a result, certain regions of the detector might have more material, leading to different levels of energy loss or scattering for particles passing through. The primary goal of this report is to study whether these variations in material budget with respect to ϕ lead to corresponding fluctuations in the impact parameter resolution.

(a) IDEA vertex detector

(b) Vertex inner barrel

Figure 1.9: The schematic of the (a) IDEA vertex detector and (b) vertex inner barrel of the IDEA vertex detector in DD4hep.

Figure 1.10: Material budget dependence on ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for the IDEA vertex detector.

2 Experimental Setup and Methods

Simulations are essential to analyze the performance of detectors, e.g., to understand the overall performance of the tracking system and study the effects of optimizing the different components of the detector.

Simulations can be conducted at varying levels of detail, such as fast simulation for speed and full simulation for accuracy using Geant4 [23]. Future collider detector geometries are implemented in DD4hep [24] to allow full simulation using the Key4hep [25] software environment, which can be used for both simulation and reconstruction of high-energy particle physics events. The DD4hep framework, as part of the key4hep ecosystem, was utilized in this report to implement the geometry and simulation setup for the IDEA vertex detector.

Two commonly used approaches for simulating the events in high-energy particle colliders are particle gun simulations and physics process simulation (e.g. $e^+e^- \rightarrow Z \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$), and both use Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. In this report, we used only particle-gun simulations and the IDEA detector response was performed using Geant4 under-the-hood.

To better understand and visualize the geometry of the IDEA vertex detector, let us again look at the CAD model of it in the Fig. 1.9a shows the IDEA vertex detector model in DD4hep.

2.1 Simulation using particle gun

A particle gun is a tool that generates single particles with predefined properties such as momentum, direction (polar angle θ and azimuthal angle ϕ), particle type (electron, muon, and proton), and charge of the particle. The particle gun shoots particles into the detector from a specified position and parameters and is used to study the performance of the detector at the single-particle level. The key aspect of a particle gun is the ability to precisely control the characteristics of the particles being fired into the detector. A particle gun can be used in ddsim, which is the simulation engine of the DD4hep framework. In this report, the simulation we used has the following options:

1. `--gun.particle`: To define the type of particle. In this report, we set this option to select only negatively charged muon.
2. `--gun.energy`: To specify the energy of the particle gun. In this report, we used this option to set it to 1 GeV, 10 GeV, and 100 GeV.

3. `--gun.thetaMin`, `--gun.thetaMax`: To specify the polar angle for the direction of the particles. In this report, we used this option to set it to $\cos(\theta) = 0, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1$.
4. `--gun.phiMin`, `--gun.phiMax`: To specify the azimuthal angle range. In this report, we used this option to set it between 0 and 45 degrees in steps of 1 degree.
5. `--numberOfEvent`: To specify the number of events to be generated. In this report, we used this option to generate 1000 events.

The output of `ddsims` is the simulated hits of the generated particles in the various layers of the detector. These hits are used for reconstruction and analysis, similar to how real experimental data is handled.

2.2 Track and vertex reconstruction

For the reconstruction, we use different setups, such as `GeoSvc`, which maps the hits to their locations in the detector. Furthermore, the module `TrackingCellIDEncodingSvc` is used to manage the encoding and decoding of cell IDs associated with tracking hits. The digitisation of the simulated hits is performed using `DDPlanarDigiProcessor`, which Gaussian-smears the simulated hits with the expected single-hit resolution of the sensors used ($3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^2$ in CLD vertex and IDEA inner vertex, and $14 \times 43 \mu\text{m}^2$ in the outer vertex barrel and disks of IDEA). Finally, tracking is done using conformal tracking, which was developed in the context of linear collider studies [26]. Both `DDPlanarDigiProcessor` and conformal tracking are called using the `k4MarlinWrapper` that enables using these Marlin algorithms inside `key4hep`.

2.3 Impact parameter resolution

The resolution of the impact parameters in the IDEA vertex detector is a key metric that indicates how good the detector is in measuring each of the five track parameters listed in Sec. 1.2. To extract the resolution of the impact parameters and other track parameters, a fit of the Gaussian distribution should be applied to the distribution of the number of hits for each of the impact and track parameters. As an example, Fig. 2.1 shows the distribution of the d_0 impact parameter for 1000 events with negatively charged muons generated by the particle gun, for $\theta = 70$, $\phi = 30$ and momentum = 100 GeV. In the plot mentioned, the Gaussian fit is applied, and the standard deviation of the Gaussian fit (the red curve) shows the resolution of the impact parameter. This is true for all five track parameters, which are not shown here.

While in Fig. 2.1 we fixed θ , in Fig. 2.2, we show the resolution of the impact parameter d_0 as a function of $\cos(\theta)$ for three different momenta of the simulated muons: 1 GeV (black), 10 GeV (red), and 100 GeV (blue). As you can see, the less momentum the gun particle has, the better the resolution of the impact parameter.

Figure 2.1: Gaussian distribution for d_0 impact parameters for $\theta = 70$, $\phi = 30$ and momentum = 100 GeV.

Figure 2.2: The resolution of the d_0 impact parameter for momentum = 1, 10, 100 GeV for different $\cos(\theta)$.

3 Results and Discussions

In this chapter, the study of the resolution of impact and track parameters as a function of the ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ coordinate parameters for particle gun muons is presented. These results help assess the performance of the vertex detector in terms of vertexing precision and provide insight into potential areas for detector optimization.

3.1 Impact parameter resolution

As discussed in previous chapters, the geometry of the CLD vertex detector is much simpler compared to the IDEA vertex detector. In the CLD vertex detector, the sensors are simply implemented along the stave; however, in the IDEA vertex detector, the design is in such a way that the sensitive part of the sensor covers the insensitive parts. Therefore, in the CLD vertex detector, there is no effect of ϕ on the resolution of the impact and tracking parameters, but this is not the case for the IDEA vertex detector. In fact, in previous studies on the material budget in Fig. 1.10, there was an oscillated dependence of ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ on the material budget. Hence, there should also be the dependence of ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ on the resolution of the impact and track parameters.

When comparing the case of the 1 GeV momentum with 10 GeV and 100 GeV in Fig. 1.5, it is shown that the effect of the material budget for the momentum equal to 1 GeV is greater than other momentum. Therefore, in this chapter, only momentum equal to 1 GeV will be discussed.

Fig. 3.1 illustrates the resolution of the impact parameter $\sigma(d_0)$ for different ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ at a momentum equal to 1 GeV. In this plot, it is shown that for small values of $\cos(\theta)$, the resolution of impact parameters improves. Therefore, the lower $\cos(\theta)$, the better the resolution of the impact parameter, as we expected from the Eq. 1.2.4, where $\sigma(d_0)$ depends on θ . This behavior is expected as more material is traversed in the barrel region, leading to improved tracking precision and better vertex resolution.

Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 3.1, and also in the projection plot for $\cos(\theta) = 0.5$, the resolution of the impact parameter d_0 changes in the order of $\mathcal{O}(\pm 22\%)$ with variation of the azimuthal angles ϕ . This was explained before; as you can see in Fig. 1.10, there is a $\mathcal{O}(\pm 5\%)$ in the material budget plot by the variation of ϕ . Using Eq. 1.3.1, this change in the material budget gives us exactly $\mathcal{O}(\pm 22\%)$ for the resolution of impact parameters. This is because, as we discussed before, the IDEA vertex detector does not perform consistently in the $r - \phi$ plane, unlike the CLD vertex detector.

Figure 3.1: Impact parameter resolution $\sigma(d_0)$ for different ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for the momentum of 1 GeV. The $\sigma(d_0)$ for $\cos(\theta) = 0.5$ and the different ϕ .

A similar plot for the 100 GeV momentum is also shown in Fig. 5.1 in the appendix. The variation is less than the 1 GeV plot, as it is of $\mathcal{O}(\pm 14\%)$ with variation of the azimuthal angle ϕ . This was expected because the higher the momentum, the lower the dependence on the resolution of the impact parameters. To further investigate the resolution of the other impact and track parameters, Fig. 3.2 is shown for momentum 1 GeV (Fig. 5.4 and Fig. 5.2 for 10 GeV and 100 GeV, respectively). This plot illustrates the resolution of the impact parameter $\sigma(z_0)$ and also tracks parameters such as $\sigma(\phi)$, $\sigma(\tan \Lambda)$, and $\sigma(\Omega)$, shown as a function of the cosine of the polar angle ($\cos(\theta)$) and azimuthal angle (ϕ).

As shown in 3.1 and Fig. 3.2, there are some gaps in the impact parameter resolution plots at $\cos(\theta) = 0.80$ with $\phi = 15, 16$, and 17 , $\cos(\theta) = 0.85$ with $\phi = 16, 17$, and 18 . The reason is that the number of hits is very low in this region, so one cannot reconstruct the tracks and, therefore, cannot apply the Gaussian distribution to analyse the track. This means that there must be a problem in the design of the vertex detector engineering and that it should be fixed in the future.

There is also the same problem for momentum equal to 100 GeV. As illustrated in the Fig. 5.2, gaps are at $\phi = 22$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.85$, and $\phi = 23$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.8$. In addition, by looking at $\cos(\theta)$, as mentioned above, the resolution of the impact parameters increases by increasing $\cos(\theta)$; however, at $\cos(\theta) = 0$, there is a sudden change. The reason should be again in the number of hits, which will be discussed in the next part.

Figure 3.2: Impact parameters and track parameters resolutions as a function of the polar angle θ and azimuthal angle ϕ for muons with a momentum of 1 GeV.

3.2 Minimum and mean number of hits

In order to study the above-mentioned problem, the plot of the mean and minimum number of hits versus ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ is plotted to see if the mean and minimum number of hits for the gaps are small or not. Therefore, the mean and minimum number of hits plotted in Fig. 3.3 for the gun momentum equals 1 GeV (Fig. 5.5 and Fig. 5.3 for 10 GeV and 100 GeV in the appendix).

In Fig. 3.3a, it is shown that the mean number of hits is mostly between 4 and 5 for different θ and ϕ . Also, Fig. 3.3b illustrates a minimum number of hits, which are different from 0 to 6, but as long as the mean number of hits is above three, the track can be reconstructed, and, therefore, the track parameters can be measured.

However, for $\cos(\theta) = 0$, both the mean and minimum number of hits are zero. This is the reason why we had a sudden change in Fig. 3.2, which was discussed before. In addition, for $\phi = 22$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.85$, 0.80 , $\phi = 23$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.80$, both the mean and minimum number of hits are small compared to other angles, as the reconstructable particle efficiencies are low here. For instance, the reconstructable particle

efficiency for $\phi = 22$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.80$ is 0.20 % (2/1000 events). Therefore, those gaps appeared in the impact parameters and track parameter resolution plots.

Figure 3.3: (a) Mean number of hits (b) minimum number of hits with respect to ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for momentum equal to 1GeV.

According to Fig. 3.4, the reason that the mean value and minimum number of hits are zero in $\cos(\theta) = 0$ and $\phi = 0$ is that there is no sensing area in the way of the particle to get detected and reconstruct the hits in this $\cos(\theta)$ direction. This is visible in the plot by the red line that hits the white area and not the sensing (yellow) area. Also, in the following vertex detector layers, a gap at $\cos(\theta) = 0$ and $\phi = 0$ is present. Therefore, due to the design problem of the vertex detector, the detector design needs to be changed to cover these gaps.

Figure 3.4: The illustration of the gaps at $\cos(\theta) = 0$ (grey lines on the detector, which is shown by following the red line hitting it).

Finally, as shown in Fig. 5.3a and Fig. 5.3b, the mean and minimum number of hits for some angles such as $\cos(\theta) = 0.25$ and $\phi = 11^\circ$ and 27° , are even lower than for $\phi = 22^\circ$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.85, 0.80$, and $\phi = 23^\circ$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.80$. Looking again at 5.2b and 5.2c, we can exactly see the gap in the mentioned angles. However, there is no gap in these angles in Fig. 5.1 and 5.2a as these two impact parameters relate to the inner barrel layers and other parameters related to the outer barrels and disks. This means

that in the mentioned angles, the hits just occurred in the inner barrel layers and not in the outer layers. This is the reason why there is no gap in the impact parameter resolutions.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

This report focused on the performance evaluation of the IDEA vertex detector using a full simulation for the FCC-ee collider, with a specific emphasis on the resolutions of the impact parameters and tracking parameters. The IDEA vertex detector, characterized by its lower material budget and more detailed geometry description compared to the CLD vertex detector, also benefits from a fully engineered design, which was a key motivation for this study.

The results demonstrated that the resolution of the impact parameters and the tracking parameters improves with increasing cosine of the polar angle ($\cos(\theta)$), which was expected from the approximation relation of the impact parameter d_0 .

The material budget of the detector has an oscillating behavior with the azimuthal angle (ϕ). Therefore, a similar oscillation was expected in the resolutions of the impact parameters and tracking parameters by varying ϕ . However, the results showed that ϕ had a negligible effect $\mathcal{O}(\pm 22\%)$ ($\mathcal{O}(\pm 14\%)$ for 100 GeV) on the resolutions of the impact parameters and the tracking parameters. Hence, the resolution is constant along the ϕ .

In this study, we found that for $\cos(\theta) = 0$, there was a sudden change in the impact parameters and the tracking parameters. Also, at $\cos(\theta) = 0.80$ with $\phi = 15, 16$, and 17 , $\cos(\theta) = 0.85$ with $\phi = 16, 17$, and 18 (for momentum equal to 100 GeV at $\phi = 22$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.85, 0.85$, $\phi = 23$ with $\cos(\theta) = 0.8$) a problem in track reconstruction was observed. The mean and mean number of registered hits were studied to investigate this issue. The study showed that the tracking failed in these regions of the detector due to a problem with the design of the vertex detector.

Future work should aim to refine the layout of the sensing elements to fix the caps in detector coverage and ensure continuous tracking performance across all angular ranges.

5 Appendix

Figure 5.1: Impact parameter resolution $\sigma(d_0)$ for different ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for the momentum of 100 GeV. The $\sigma(d_0)$ for $\cos(\theta) = 0.5$ and the different ϕ .

Figure 5.2: Impact parameters and track parameters resolutions as a function of the polar angle θ and azimuthal angle ϕ for muons with a momentum of 100 GeV.

Figure 5.3: (a) Mean number of hits and (b) minimum number of hits with respect to ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for momentum equal to 100 GeV.

Figure 5.4: for momentum equal to 10GeV.

Figure 5.5: (a) Mean number of hits (b) minimum number of hits with respect to ϕ and $\cos(\theta)$ for momentum equal to 10GeV.

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